
Swami Dayananda Saraswati and Arya Samaj: Liberation of Hyderabad Movement

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14792576

Abstract:

Swami Dayananda Saraswati established the Arya Samaj in Bombay in 1875. He desired to Reform Hindu society by removing the socio-religious evils through Samaj. The Arya samaj Among the major socio-religions movements of India, the Arya Samaj played a pivotal role in spreading the socio-political renaissance in Nizam's dominion. The Arya Samaj Movement took a political colour in Hyderabad State.

Keywords: *Liberation of Hyderabad and Swami Dayanand Saraswati Arya Samaj*

Historical Background:

Swami Dayananda Saraswati established the Arya Samaj in Bombay in 1875. He desired to Reform Hindu society by removing the socio-religious evils through Samaj. The Arya samaj Among the major socio-religions movements of India, the Arya Samaj played a pivotal role in spreading the socio-political renaissance in Nizam's dominion. The Arya Samaj Movement took a political colour in Hyderabad State. In his magnum-opus work 'Satyarth Prakash' throws light on his views. Dayananda was great propagator of 'Shuddi Movement' and he gave the slogans like "India for Indians and back to Vedas". After the death of Dayanand in 1883, his mission was carried further by his followers like Mahatma Hans Raj, Guru Datta Vidyarthi, Lala Lajpat Rai, Munshi Ram and others.

Introduction:

Arya Samaj, founded in 1875 at Bombay by Maharishi Dayanand Saraswathi, has been hailed as one of the most potential and dynamic socio-religious

movements of the day. The Arya Samaj was mainly responsible in bringing the region into the main stream of Indian nationalism. It had a great impact on the life and thinking of the people particularly of the Hindus in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Historical Role in Hyderabad liberation movement to Arya Samaj:

Arya Samaj, founded in 1875 at Bombay by Maharishi Dayanand Saraswathi, has been hailed as one of the most potential and dynamic socio-religious movements of the day. It had a great impact on the life and thinking of the people particularly of the Hindus in the 19th and 20th centuries. According to Dr.K.P.Jaiswal, "The foundation of the Arya Samaj marked the beginning of vital changes in the social, religious, educational and national life of the vast majority of the people of India, as well as among the followers of the various faiths of the world. "Speaking on the role of Arya Samaj, Yogi Arvind Ghosh of Pondichery said,

"Dayanand was the real harbinger of the

Indian Renaissance which opened up new directions and fresh hopes for millions of people who were groaning under the worst kind of slavery resulting from social, religious, cultural and political decadence."

In the light of the above statements the role of the Arya Samaj during the latter part of the reign of the last Nizam, Osman Ali Khan becomes very clear. The Arya Samaj in Hyderabad gave an impetus to the political awakening and paved the way for political emancipation at Hyderabad.

The Nizam Government in a bid to establish the Islamic State denied opportunities for the people of non-ruling class to enjoy basic civil and human rights. Arya Samaj, under these circumstances could not be a silent spectator. The Nizam mixed religion and politics and encouraged the 'Ittehad' to start Tableegh, and issued farman (order) and passed the acts called Mufusa and Gayar Mufusa. It the first one protected the property of the Muslims and those of converted, the second Act empowered Muslims have enslaved the Hindus, by purchasing the lands of the Hindus who mortgaged them on their debts. Many of the Hindu people agitated against the orders of the Government through Arya Samaj. They propagated the message of Arya-Samaj; (a) Equality of all human beings, (b) Condemnation of caste system, (c) Equal opportunities of education and refinement, (d) The message of 'Satyarth Prakash' i.e., "Back to Vedas". Inspired the enthusiastic and fearless patriots of Hyderabad Karnataka

This satyagraha has been considered an important landmark in the history of Hyderabad freedom struggle and the government in recognition of it has been honouring those who bravely participated in it by granting pensions to them. Snathak in 1990, writes that several Satyagrahis came from outside Hyderabad also to join the Satyagraha. Leaders from Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Hyderabad, and Gujarat

emerged as 'dictators' in different phases of the Satyagraha. They put forth fourteen major demands before the Nizam's Government. Initially, the State Congress and All India Congress were critical of the Satyagraha but when they saw the success it achieved the congratulatory messages poured in from all of them. Mahatma Gandhi also gave special commendation Brahmadatt concludes, "I was only 20 years old then and the only child of my parents, it gives great pride that the Satyagraha has been recognized by the Indian Government as a part of the National Freedom Struggle" Regarding the reaction the of the Muslims in the state, the Muslims of Hyderabad in February, 1939 submitted a memorandum to Sir Akbar Hydari pointing out the indifference of state towards the agitation started by the Arya Samaj and warning that if the movement was not suppressed within a fortnight they would come forward to combat the agitation on behalf of the state, and the ruler who belonged to the Muslims and not bother about the consequences that might follow.

Conclusion:

It is summarized from the above discussion that Arya Samaj played significant role in uniting people of all Hindu castes. By making such efforts, it opened its branches all over India. As such, it responded to the many local problems such as socio-reforms in Hyderabad-Karnataka. Many of the leaders of Arya Samaj such as Swami Ramanand Teerth have made organized struggle against the atrocities of Razakars and the Nizam's rule in the region. Due to their efforts Hyderabad State including Hyderabad-Karnataka area merged into the Indian Union in September 1948. Hence, the efforts of Arya Samaj and leaders of Arya Samaj are worth to remembered in the history of liberation of Hyderabad-Karnataka region. It can be said that the reforms of Arya Samaj are of great

significance and have made huge impacts on the contemporary Hindu society. The Arya Samaj has become a major acculturative movement with its purified Hinduism.

End notes and references:

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